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CHALLENGES OF PROVIDING EDUCATION IN PRISONS: ANALYSIS OF THE EHPC PRACTICE AND PERSPECTIVES FOR MOLDOVA

This article focuses on the implementation of the right to education for prisoners in penitentiary institutions using information technology. The main emphasis is placed on the analysis of international and national legal acts, the case law of the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR), as well as a comparative study of practices in various countries in this field. The article examines key ECHR cases that highlight the importance of upholding the right to education for prisoners and minimizing restrictions on this right. The analysis also explores the potential for introducing digital education in Moldovan penitentiary institutions, focusing on the enhancement of digital infrastructure, the training of personnel, and the design of tailored educational programs. The article concludes by offering recommendations on incorporating information technologies into prison education, which aids in developing prisoners' digital competencies, supports their successful reintegration into society, and helps reduce the likelihood of reoffending.

Keywords: prisoner education, information technology, human rights, education digitization, reintegration.

PROBLEMELE ASIGURĂRII EDUCAȚIEI ÎN ÎNCHISORI: ANALIZA PRACTICII CEDO ȘI PERSPECTIVE PENTRU MOLDOVA

Acest articol este dedicat studiului implementării dreptului la educație pentru deținuți în instituțiile penitenciare, utilizând tehnologiile informaționale. Atenția principală este acordată analizei actelor juridice internaționale și naționale, practicii Curții Europene a Drepturilor Omului (CEDO), precum și studiului comparativ al practicilor din diferite țări în acest domeniu. Articolul examinează cazuri-cheie ale CEDO, care subliniază importanța respectării dreptului la educație al deținuților și minimizarea restricțiilor asupra acestui drept. Se analizează, de asemenea, posibilitățile de digitalizare a educației în instituțiile penitenciare din Republica Moldova, inclusiv dezvoltarea infrastructurii digitale, formarea personalului și crearea unor programe educaționale adaptate. În concluzia articolului sunt propuse recomandări pentru implementarea tehnologiilor informaționale în procesul educațional al penitenciarelor, ceea ce contribuie la dezvoltarea abilităților digitale ale deținuților, la reintegrarea lor de succes în societate și la reducerea recidivismului.

Cuvinte-cheie: educația deținuților, tehnologii informaționale, drepturile omului, digitalizarea educației, reintegrare.

1. INTRODUCTION.

The implementation of information technologies in educational programs of penitentiary institutions plays a crucial role in their reform. Today, we face a lack of effective methods for integrating IT, which limits the opportunities for inmates to receive quality education. Addressing this problem requires a comprehensive approach that includes legislative, organizational, and technical measures.

The use of IT can significantly improve the educational process for inmates by expanding access to educational resources and creating a flexible learning environment tailored to the individual needs of each person. The introduction of online courses, digital libraries, and interactive learning materials is a vital step towards achieving these goals.

However, several key challenges need to be addressed for the successful implementation of IT. Firstly, it is essential to modernize the infrastructure of penitentiary institutions, ensuring access to the internet and necessary technical equipment. It is also important to develop educational programs for staff to effectively use IT and support inmates in the learning process.

Creating a legal framework to regulate the use of IT includes developing data security standards and protocols for information protection. This will help ensure the safe and effective use of internet resources in penitentiary institutions.

2. METHODOLOGY.

The study used various methods to comprehensively examine the implementation of the right to education for inmates in penitentiary institutions using IT. The following approaches were applied in the research: analysis of legal documents, where international and national laws were studied, including the European Convention on Human Rights, the Constitution of the Republic of Moldova, national legislation, and decisions of the European Court of Human Rights [10]. Review of judicial practice, specifically the analysis of key ECHR cases concerning the right to education for inmates, to identify precedents and emphasize the im-

portance of upholding this right. Comparative analysis of practices in different countries was conducted to study international practices of IT implementation in the educational process of penitentiary institutions, which allowed identifying best practices and common problems. An assessment of the current state of digitalization of education in Moldovan penitentiary institutions was carried out. These methods allowed for the identification of the necessity to implement information technologies in the educational process of prisoners, which will contribute to the development of their digital skills and their successful reintegration into society.

3. RESULTS.

3.1. Implementation of IT in the Development of Digital Skills.

The need for inmates to study and use information technologies contributes to the development of digital skills necessary for the modern labor market. This approach increases the chances of convicted individuals for successful reintegration into society. It is essential that the resocialization of inmates is carried out within the framework of legality and also ensures the safety of society. It is important to emphasize that inmates also need access to cultural, sports, and recreational activities, which are essential for maintaining psychological balance and fostering the development of personal qualities.

International standards of the right to education, as noted by Matyusheva T.N., are «a set of educational norms shared by all civilized nations and peoples, having universal significance» [5, p.14]. It should be noted that these standards are mandatory for states participating in international integration processes and are contained in various international documents. The proper definition of international standards of the right to education highlights the importance of ensuring equal rights to education.

In the context of international standards and the practice of the European Court of Human Rights, the fundamental right of convicted individuals to education is emphasized. The ECHR has repeatedly stressed that the right to education should be accessible to all, including convicted individuals, and its decisions further

emphasize the necessity of creating conditions for both education and professional training of prisoners.

3.2 Examples from ECHR Practice: The Importance of Upholding the Right to Education.

The concept of examples from ECHR practice highlights the importance of upholding this right and emphasizes that restrictions on education should be minimal and justified. International practice shows that inmates have the right to education according to international law, and violations of this right can be challenged in international courts.

For example, in the case of Mehmet Reşit Arslan and Orhan Bingöl v. Turkey, the inmates appealed to the ECHR in 2006, claiming that their right to education, guaranteed by Article 2, Protocol 1 of the European Convention on Human Rights [10], had been violated.

Mehmet Reşit Arslan was sentenced to life imprisonment in 1992, and Orhan Bingöl in 1995. On March 13, 2006, Arslan applied to the administration of İzmir Type F Prison, expressing his desire to use a computer with internet access in prison. Law №. 5275 on the Execution of Penalties and Security Measures provides that inmates can use computers with controlled internet access in certain areas and within rehabilitation or training courses. However, these rights can be restricted when considered dangerous or when it involves inmates convicted of terrorism.

Arslan's request was denied on the grounds that he «maintained connections within the prison with other inmates belonging to the same illegal organization and that he was not attending any training courses» [3]. In response, Arslan appealed to the Execution Court, stating that before his conviction, he was a final-year medical student and wanted access to audiovisual materials to continue his studies. He also offered to pay for the necessary equipment himself. After reviewing his complaint, the Execution Court rejected Arslan's application.

Challenging this rejection in the High Criminal Court, Arslan's application was again denied. The High Criminal Court ruled that the court's decision «did not violate procedure or

law». Arslan submitted a similar application to Bolu Type F Prison, where he was later transferred. However, he faced the same process, ending with the rejection of his request. Different prisons, same decision.

Orhan Bingöl, an inmate in a Type F prison in Kocaeli, also applied to the prison administration on August 1, 2006, expressing his desire to use a computer. However, his request was initially denied by the prison administration and subsequently by the courts he appealed to. The European Court of Human Rights issued a decision regarding the two inmates who had sought to continue their university education 13 years earlier [11]. The court found that their right to education had been violated. However, it did not award compensation for material or moral damages as the applicants had not requested it [3].

Thus, the case of Mehmet Reşit Arslan and Orhan Bingöl underscores the importance of protecting the educational and informational rights of those serving sentences in penitentiary institutions and the necessity of upholding procedural rights for inmates.

Another example is the case of Jankovskis v. Lithuania (January 17, 2017). The applicant, a prisoner, complained that he was denied access to the website of the Ministry of Education and Science, which would have provided him with educational information [11], in violation of Article 10 of the ECHR [8]. This case was not about the refusal of the authorities to provide requested information but rather the applicant's complaint about the means of access-specifically, the internet-to publicly available information on a freely accessible website. He needed internet access to continue his university studies, but his request was denied.

The ECHR stated: «In reviewing the decisions of the Lithuanian authorities, the Court cannot overlook that their main focus was on the legal prohibition of prisoners' access to the internet as such, rather than considering the applicant's argument that access to a specific website was necessary for his education» (§ 61) [11]. The Court further remarked: «Finally, the Court takes into account the fact that in a number of documents of the Council of Europe

and other international documents, the importance of the internet for public services and its significance for exercising a wide range of human rights has been recognized. Access to the internet is increasingly understood as a right, and calls have been made to develop effective policies to achieve universal access to the internet and to overcome the 'digital divide' (§ 62). The ECHR «is not convinced that sufficient reasons have been put forward to justify the interference with the applicant's right to receive information» (§ 63) and ruled in favor of the applicant. The ECHR's recommendations emphasize the need for policies that effectively address the «digital divide». Measures must be taken to ensure that the effective right to education is combined with the application of necessary security measures, which will help avoid discrimination that could undermine the goal of providing education and supporting the reintegration of inmates. The ECHR emphasizes the need to establish legal frameworks to address new circumstances arising from digital culture and reality [2].

This example shows that access to the internet is increasingly recognized as a right, and that the violation of this right can be considered a human rights violation, such as the right to education. The ECHR urges states to take measures to ensure universal access to the internet and to overcome the "digital divide."

In the context of the Republic of Moldova, the right to free access to information and freedom of expression are guaranteed by the Constitution of Moldova [4], as well as by international agreements such as the European Convention on Human Rights. Furthermore, Moldova recognizes the importance of the internet and is actively improving its policies in the areas of digital development and internet access. The Republic of Moldova has adopted the National Digital Transformation Strategy for 2023-2030 [7], which aims to accelerate the integration of digital technologies into all spheres of the country's life. The strategy provides for the development of digital services and the improvement of internet accessibility, as well as the enhancement of digital skills among the population. It also envisions the

introduction of new technologies, the development of innovative products and services, and the establishment of a legal framework for digital transformation and the development of digital infrastructure.

The strategy aligns with European and international standards, promotes sustainable development, and aims to prepare Moldova for a digital future. To maintain its relevance and adapt to the rapidly changing world of technology, the strategy will be reviewed annually [6].

However, as in other countries, there are issues with Internet accessibility in remote and impoverished regions of Moldova, which can lead to violations of human rights regarding free access to information and freedom of expression. Therefore, further efforts are needed to bridge the digital divide and ensure universal access to the Internet in Moldova.

A third case is *Kalda v. Estonia* (ECHR, 2016). In its judgment of January 19, 2016, the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) partially restricted prisoners' access to the Internet [7]. Although Article 10 on freedom of expression of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR – Council of Europe, 2013) cannot be considered a source of an absolute right for prisoners to access the Internet, the judges in Strasbourg nonetheless require that any interference with prisoners' right to receive information through this medium be «prescribed by law» [12].

This judgment (*Kalda v. Estonia*) became final under Article 44 § 2 of the Convention. The case began with a complaint by Romeo Kalda (No. 17429/10) to the European Court of Human Rights against the Republic of Estonia on March 16, 2010. The applicant claimed that his right under Article 10 of the Convention to receive information via the Internet without interference by a public authority had been violated (Article 10.1). Article 10 of the ECHR regulates freedom of expression and involves restricting prisoners' access to certain websites containing legal information. The applicant, Mr. Romeo Kalda, is a prisoner who complained that he was hindered in conducting legal research due to being denied access to certain Internet sites [12]. These included the

website of the local Information Office of the Council of Europe and some, but not all, state databases containing laws and court decisions.

During the appellate proceedings initiated by the applicant, the Supreme Court concluded that providing access to Internet sites other than those permitted by the prison administration could increase the risk of prisoners engaging in prohibited communications, which would require enhanced monitoring of their computer use [1].

3.3 Restrictions on Prisoners' Access to Information via the Internet: Legal Analysis under Article 10 ECHR.

The requirement revolves around Article 10 of the ECHR. It is not about the authorities' refusal to provide the requested information. Rather, the applicant's complaint concerned the specific means of access, namely via the Internet, to information published on certain websites that are freely and publicly accessible.

The conditions associated with the status of a prisoner-deprivation of liberty-inevitably entail a number of restrictions on prisoners' communication with the outside world, including the ability to obtain information. Article 10 of the ECHR cannot be interpreted as imposing a general obligation on authorities to provide prisoners with Internet access or access to specific websites. However, in this case, prisoners were granted limited Internet access under domestic law, including access to official legislative and judicial databases. Nonetheless, the restriction of access to other sites that also contained legal information violated the applicant's right to receive information. The interference was prescribed by law and pursued legitimate aims such as protecting the rights of others and preventing disorder and crime: «In this regard, the Court reiterates that, in view of its accessibility and ability to store and communicate vast amounts of information, the Internet plays an important role in enhancing the public's access to news and facilitating the dissemination of information in general» [1].

This example demonstrates that Article 10 of the ECHR, which guarantees the freedom to receive and impart information, can be violated when access to information via the Inter-

net is restricted. However, in the context of restrictions related to the status of a prisoner, this right can be limited by law if such restrictions are necessary to achieve legitimate aims, such as protecting the rights of others or preventing disorder and crime. This case exemplifies how the lack of access to education in prison conditions can lead to the violation of not only the right to education but also other rights of prisoners, such as the right to freedom and protection from torture and inhuman treatment [13].

Prolonged lack of access to education in prison conditions violates the right to education, guaranteed by Article 2 of Protocol No. 1 to the ECHR [9], which recognizes the right to education without discrimination. Moreover, the lack of access to education can have negative consequences for the prisoner, such as insufficient preparation for life after release and limited opportunities for participation in social life, which can lead to further violations of other rights of the prisoner.

Thus, the court's decision underscores the importance of ensuring access to education for convicted individuals in penitentiaries as a means of preparing them for life after release. This provides opportunities for participation in social life and is also part of the right to education, which is guaranteed to all people without discrimination.

3.4 International Experience and Recommendations.

Various documents of the Council of Europe and international legal acts recognize access to the internet as a right and emphasize the importance of creating effective policies to ensure internet access while eliminating the "digital divide." At the present stage in society, more and more services and information are provided exclusively online.

Based on the analysis of international practice, it is evident that the implementation of digitalization in education within penitentiary institutions faces the challenge of balancing freedom and security. In a certain sense, this creates obstacles to the effective realization of the fundamental rights of prisoners, which should be preserved rather than annulled. These issues may arise due to the complexity of

using digital technologies and their limitations, which are influenced by the conditions of imprisonment and the structural characteristics of penitentiary institutions. However, these difficulties can be overcome.

The implementation of digital technologies can prevent the digital divide from becoming a factor of social isolation, which is particularly important for the reintegration of inmates into society after release. The primary goal of the penitentiary system—rehabilitation and successful reintegration—requires preparing inmates for future life in society. This is impossible without incorporating digital reality into the educational process; otherwise, education only exacerbates the “digital divide,” which contradicts modern realities. Therefore, it is necessary to develop and implement digital educational technologies in penitentiary institutions. This will enable inmates to acquire the necessary skills for successful integration into the digital society, reduce the risk of social isolation, and increase their chances of successful adaptation and employment after release.

4. CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, it is emphasized that ensuring the right to education for inmates

through the implementation of IT requires a systematic approach and interdisciplinary collaboration. The effective realization of this initiative demands active participation from government bodies, international organizations, the academic community, and civil society.

A comparative analysis of practices in different countries shows that integrating IT into the educational process of penitentiary institutions requires a comprehensive approach that takes into account both technological and social aspects. Global experience confirms that access to digital educational resources fosters the development of digital skills necessary for the successful reintegration of inmates into society.

A practical analysis of the state of digitalization of education in penitentiary institutions in Moldova has revealed the need for system reform. The development of infrastructure, increased accessibility of internet technologies, the creation of digital educational programs, and the training of personnel can significantly improve the quality of education and facilitate the successful reintegration of inmates into society.

The implementation of digital educational technologies in penitentiary institutions represents an important step towards creating a more just and inclusive society.

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